

ENHANCING VOCABULARY PROFICIENCY IN INDONESIAN FOR FOREIGN SPEAKERS
(BIPA) THROUGH CARD GAMES

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ABSTRAK

Program Program BIPA bertujuan membantu penutur asing mempelajari Bahasa Indonesia untuk berbagai tujuan, seperti akademik, profesional, atau komunikasi sehari-hari. Bahasa Indonesia memiliki eksistensi yang signifikan di seluruh dunia, dan BIPA berkembang baik di dalam maupun di luar negeri. Dengan popularitasnya yang terus meningkat, Bahasa Indonesia memiliki potensi besar untuk menjadi bahasa internasional. Dalam rangka mencapai tujuan tersebut, program pembelajaran BIPA mencakup keterampilan berbahasa Indonesia seperti berbicara, menulis, membaca, dan mendengarkan untuk pembelajar asing. Selain itu, penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menguji manfaat permainan kartu kata dan kartu gambar dalam meningkatkan kosakata Bahasa Indonesia bagi pembelajar tingkat tinggi atau dewasa, serta untuk mengevaluasi persepsi pembelajar terhadap permainan kartu ini.

Kata Kunci: Penguasaan, Kisakata, BIPA, Permainan Kartu.

PENDAHULUAN

Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) is expanding and taught not only internationally but also domestically. Currently, Indonesian is offered at over 45 institutions within the country. The objective of BIPA instruction, both at home and abroad, is to enable foreign students to communicate effectively in Indonesian. Therefore, choosing the appropriate teaching strategies is essential to achieve this goal.

The BIPA program is designed to help non-native speakers learn and become proficient in Indonesian for academic, professional, and everyday communication. The significance of Indonesian language is emphasized by Purwo (as cited in Purwadi, 2019), who established the Indonesian widespread use due to its ranking as the third most common language in WordPress posts.

Approximately 4,463,950 speakers of Indonesian reside overseas, making it a widely spoken language internationally. In Australia, it is recognized as one of the more prevalent languages. The global interest in learning Indonesian is reflected in BIPA program reach. By the end of 2020, 355 institutions in 41 countries offered the BIPA programs to a total of 72,746 students. The Ministry of Education and Culture has supported 146 institutions across 29 countries. These figures show the concerted efforts by the Ministry of Education and Culture, alongside the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, to promote Indonesian as an international language and a tool for soft power diplomacy.

The popularity of Indonesian suggests it could become an international language. BIPA program, which includes formal and informal educational settings, aims to develop the speaking, writing, reading, listening, and comprehension skills of foreign students. In case Indonesian achieve international language status, the benefits could be significant, enhancing cultural diplomacy, and potentially increasing tourism and investment. Moreover, it would project a positive national image. To support this goal, BIPA requires well-structured learning strategies and specially designed audiovisual materials.

The vision of BIPA program is "The realization of BIPA learning enhances a positive image of Indonesia on the international stage to establish Indonesian as a widely-used language" According to the Ministry of Education and Culture website, the missions of the BIPA program are:

- A. Introducing Indonesian society and culture to the international community to enhance the country image abroad.
- B. Strengthening cooperation and expanding networks with institutions that offer BIPA education, both domestically and internationally.
- C. Providing support and facilitation to institutions offering BIPA education, both domestically and internationally.
- D. Enhancing the quality of BIPA education, both domestically and internationally.
- E. Improving the quality of resources for BIPA education, both domestically and internationally (Badan Bahasa, 2012).

The BIPA curriculum covers a various topic, such as greetings, self-introductions, daily activities, cuisine, family, education, culture, and tourism. Additionally, it introduces participants to common Indonesian expressions and phrases, enhancing their linguistic abilities and cultural insight. Active participation in the BIPA program empowers non-native speakers to communicate more effectively in Indonesian and to gain a deeper appreciation of

its culture.

This study aims to enhance understanding of Indonesian language, facilitating communication with native speakers in everyday contexts. BIPA help students gain the ability to engage with locals, comprehend instructions, and articulate themselves in daily activities. Additionally, the program supports educational pursuits, as students may seek to continue their academic journeys in Indonesia, a distinguished and appealing study destination.

BIPA is taught both in Indonesia and abroad with the primary goal of enabling international students to communicate effectively and accurately in Indonesian. Choosing the right teaching strategies is crucial to achieving this goal. An effective language learning process includes natural and meaningful communication, where students prioritize understanding the message over memorizing language rules. Strategies should foster correct and efficient communication, the application of acquired vocabulary, and the enhancement of speaking abilities. An interactive learning environment between students and teachers is essential. Moreover, language proficiency necessitates a robust vocabulary to ensure the clear articulation of ideas.

In Indonesia, numerous universities offer BIPA programs, allowing foreign students to study the language. These programs also provide opportunities for BIPA teachers. Moreover, BIPA serves as a platform for Indonesia to show its ideology, politics, society, arts, and culture. In addition, BIPA program, of the Ministry of Education and Culture dispatches ambassadors annually to teach Indonesian and represent the nation's diverse arts and cultural heritage.

Comprehending vocabulary is fundamental to language acquisition. Nation (2007) highlighted its significance in all language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. A substantial vocabulary bolsters language proficiency since language is composed of systematically combined elements to express meaning. Therefore, a wide-ranging vocabulary makes communication more fluid. In BIPA education, the emphasis on communication emphasizes cultural aspects within the social context. The goal of this approach is to cultivate non-native speakers who can proficiently utilize Indonesian for everyday interactions across diverse environments

Rachmawati (2021:2) outlined key reasons for the critical role of vocabulary enhancement in language learning. Firstly, vocabulary development is an ongoing process. Secondly, an individual understanding of the semantics of a word is intertwined with their daily vocabulary use. Thirdly, there is a strong interrelationship among words in a language. Lastly, vocabulary knowledge is integral to grasping sentence structure and grammatical concepts.

As language educators, possessing a range of methods, tactics, and teaching aids for vocabulary is essential. These tools enable students to learn in an engaging and enthusiastic environment, often through gamified experiences such as playing games or solving puzzles. This method immerses them in the rich vocabulary of foreign language without the feel of conventional study. Educational media, serving as tools to transmit instructional content, can be any intermediary that facilitates the transfer of information from the teacher to students.

Educational playing cards are forms of teaching media that resemble standard playing cards used in games such as poker or bridge. However, they are specifically designed to

impart knowledge, with a focus on affixes in this context. While these educational cards feature familiar figures such as jokers, queens, jacks, and kings, they are embellished with vibrant colors and tailored to meet the learning needs of BIPA participants. The cards visually present affixes to facilitate the understanding of affixation, which is the process of forming new words by adding affixes to a base form (Rohmadi et al., 2009, p. 41).

Affixes are linguistic elements that attach to words, altering or enhancing their meanings. Speakers of the Indonesian language are familiar with various types of affixes, such as prefixes, suffixes, infixes, and confixes. Prefixes are added to the beginning of a word, suffixes to the end, infixes within the word, and confixes are a combination of prefixes and suffixes. For teaching Indonesian vocabulary to BIPA students at the A-1 level, card games featuring words and picture cards are used. The BIPA program categorizes students into different levels as follows:

No.	Level Name	Level	Criteria
1.	BIPA1	A1-A2	Beginner
2.	BIPA2	B1-B2	Intermediate
3.	BIPA3	C1-C2	Proficient

BIPA 1 includes levels A-1 and A-2, with clear learning achievement parameters in terms of knowledge. By the end of these levels, students are expected to attain basic competence in Indonesian for everyday conversations understand and use simple expressions and communicate effectively with cooperative speakers. At this basic level, students acquire foundational skills in listening, speaking, grammar, writing, and reading, along with additional insights into Indonesian culture.

BIPA 2, includes levels B-1 and B-2, sets learning achievement parameters in knowledge, among other areas. Students are expected to use Indonesian effectively in both spoken and written forms for formal contexts and be proficient in articulating experiences, aspirations, intentions, and detailed plans with justifications, pertinent to everyday and professional scenarios. Additionally, students ought to be able to narrate events and articulate both abstract and concrete ideas within their fields of interest. At this level, students deepen their understanding of listening, speaking, grammar, writing, and reading skills, and expand their knowledge of Indonesian culture.

BIPA 3, covering levels C-1 and C-2, sets advanced knowledge goals for students. At this stage, students are expected to articulate opinions and provide reasoning in formal discussions and to compose essays. It is essential to comprehend complex texts, infer implicit meanings, and convey ideas clearly and spontaneously in structured and detailed language. This proficient level of BIPA emphasizes advanced skills in listening, speaking, grammar, writing, and reading, enriched with in-depth cultural insights into Indonesia.

This study examines the impact of card games on BIPA Level A-1 students retention and application of Indonesian vocabulary. It is motivated by common difficulties in recalling previously learned words, using them appropriately in sentences, and avoiding irrelevant or monotonous language. Furthermore, students often default to overly simplistic sentences and limited vocabulary.

The study examines the effectiveness of word card games and picture card in enhancing the recall and expansion of Indonesian vocabulary among advanced and adult students. Additionally, it aims to gauge students' perceptions of these card games. The teaching goals

include both broad and specific objectives. The broad objectives include to 1) foster an appreciation and pride in using Indonesian language, 2) encourage disciplined thinking and speech, and 3) cultivate enjoyment and comprehension of Indonesian literature.

METODE PENELITIAN

This study uses a descriptive method to detail the observable realities of teaching Indonesian vocabulary through play to beginner-level non-native speakers (Subana and Sudrajat, 2009: 26-27). According to Nababan (1993: 5), an effective teacher aims to use the best teaching methods and tools. Such methods enhance the teaching and learning process, ensuring learning objectives are achieved. The instruments used in this study include questionnaires, interviews, and multiple-choice tests, with the researcher also fulfilling the role of teacher. The questionnaire is based on a Likert scale, featuring 10 questions with four answer-choices each, as outlined in the following table.

No.	Answer	Answer Code	Score
1.	Strongly Agree	SA	8
2.	Agree	A	6
3.	Disagree	D	3
4.	Strongly Disagree	SD	2
5.	Very Strongly Disagree	VSD	1

The strategy for BIPA teaching outlines a framework for Indonesian language skill development, aiming for effective and efficient learning. To tailor this method, interviews featuring open-ended, context-specific questions are conducted to discern students needs and their views on the teaching methods and materials used.

Facilities and infrastructure play a critical role in the learning process. For instance, well-equipped and comfortable classrooms contribute to increased creativity. There are two types of classrooms: traditional and individual. During the data processing phase, pre-test scores are compared to post-test scores to assess progress.

The subjects of this study are eight students who are foreign BIPA students at level A-1 as shown below.

No.	Name	Indonesian Name	Age	Gender
1.	Lee Donghyuck	Mahen	19	Male
2.	Kim Heeyoung	Ana	17	Female
3.	Oliver Roy	Kevin	18	Male
4.	Tawan Sangpotechapai	Toni	19	Male
5.	Kane Phan	Eka	17	Male
6.	Millie joy	Ratih	19	Female
7.	Na Jihan	Putri	18	Female
8.	Sabrina Aghata	Ayu	19	Female

This study was conducted at the Brilliant English Course (BEC) located on Tuka Dalung Street in Badung Regency, Bali. The goal of the beginner-level BIPA program was to enable students to practice communication skills and accurately guess words within each given factual category.

Using word guessing games for vocabulary learning has shown effectiveness in both

teaching and retention of words used in daily life. Furthermore, the vocabulary that appear simple to native Indonesian speakers can reflect the social and cultural nuances of everyday life in Indonesia. Students express their understanding of this orally.

In beginner-level BIPA classes, card games offer a distinct advantage over standard quizzes by removing timeconstraint. Each student endeavors to guess the word on their card, continuing until they exhaust their vocabulary knowledge. The activity begins with a student sitting with their back to the screen, which displays the card to be guessed. This student attempts to guess the word on the card using hints provided by their classmates. To facilitate the guessing, memory, and thought process, the words are categorized. This makes it easier for students to recall vocabulary associated with each category. Below are the key steps followed:

- A. The teacher divides the class into four groups, each with two students. These groups engage in timed games where they match word card to corresponding picture card and identify the word class for each piece of vocabulary. The group that completes the task successfully within the time limit receives a reward. Each set of word and picture card features new vocabulary to challenge students.
- B. Subsequently, each student form simple sentences using words that are affixed to the Styrofoam displayed at the front of the class.
- C. After successfully guessing all card, students in the guessing seat choose a classmate to take their place. This process continues with each students taking turns to guess card in one category. All categories feature common vocabulary used in everyday communication and life in Indonesia.

All categories of questions are examples of vocabulary found daily and used in communication in Indonesia.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Play, defined by its enjoyment, can render the learning process more engaging and intuitive. The use of word guessing games for vocabulary acquisition is effective in BIPA programs, particularly for beginners. These games help students apply their new skills to daily communication in Indonesia, meeting their learning objectives of effective conversation with native Indonesian speakers and cultural understanding.

Each student adopts a unique approach to language application. School teachers frequently employ a standardized framework for language instruction that includes the learning process, vocabulary acquisition, and mastery. This includes memorizing vocabulary introduced at the start of each session and presenting it in the following class. Language practice with the teacher varies from short stories to extensive essays, and students also independently work on assignments provided by the teacher.

KESIMPULAN

In conclusion, the learning strategy for BIPA followed a structured method to enhance language skills efficiently and effectively. BIPA instructional methods included card games, question-and-answer sessions, demonstrations, field trips, problem-solving, discussions, experiments, group work, socio-dramas, and assignments. These methods aimed at understanding and broadening Indonesian vocabulary.

The initial challenge students faced in understanding and expanding their vocabulary could be overcome. Conversely, they experience considerable help when learning through

word and picture card games. Therefore, in future teaching and learning sessions, there is a need for an increased emphasis on gamification methods and the use of supportive educational media.

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